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GLOBAL MANAGERIAL ISSUES AND THEIR EFFECT ON OPERATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN SELECTED FAST-FOOD FIRMS IN ABIA STATE

Adaobi Nkeiruka Umeh and Obinna Chukwudi Ezeagu

Department of Business Administration,
Michael Okpara University of Agriculture,
Umudike
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Abstract: This study analysed the effect of global managerial challenges on organizational performance (A study of selected fast-food industry in Umuahia Abia state). The specific objectives included: (a) determine the effect of the leadership behaviour/styles on the survival of fast-foods in Abia State. (b) Examine the extent to which the management structure of fast-foods influences the sustainability of fast-foods in Abia State. (c) determine the effect of work conditions on the profitability of fast-foods in Abia State, and (d) ascertain the effect of managerial competence on the effectiveness of fast-foods in Abia State. Survey research design was adopted. A total of 145 questionnaire was administered to the staff of selected fast-food industry in Umuahia Abia state. Frequency distribution and percentages was determined, the hypotheses were tested using regression analysis and Spearman correlation coefficients with the help of SPSS version 25.0. The findings indicate that; Leadership behaviour/styles has significant effect on the survival of Fast-foods in Abia State., Managerial structure has significant influence on the sustainability of Fast-foods in Abia State., Work conditions has significant effect on the profitability of Fast-foods in Abia state and Managerial competence has significant effect on the effectiveness of fast-foods in Abia State. The study recommended that; CEO/Manager of fast-food should possess good leadership behaviour/styles in order to improve on the survival of Fast-foods in Umuahia as initiating structure and consideration, motivation and vision, employee-oriented and production-oriented, coercion and motivation are variable tools for organizational survival. Finally, there is need to improve and continuously adjust to good and effective managerial structure to help carry out works and other responsibilities effectively and efficiently by employees of Fast-foods in Umuahia Abia state in other to foster maintain their sustainability.

Keywords: Global Managerial Challenges, Organizational Performance

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INTRODUCTION

Management is a child of the 19th and 20th centuries (Ngige, 2014). During the early part of the 20th century most Europeans and Asians, were still very skeptical about management. For instance, when in 1924 Mary Parker Follet gave a management seminar at the Oxford University, London, they cajoled her and made mockery of her, thinking that she is just bringing to them another important American fad and in those years, the communist countries too were quite certain that management was a capitalist invention which has absolutely no meaning for them and was indeed totally incompatible with anything that could be called “Socialist” or “Marxist”. These people and countries were still very skeptical about management then because it was something that fitted others, but had very little relevance to them, their own companies and institutions and their own countries (Ngige, 2014). As social institutions go (i.e. in the early part of the 20th century), management is thus a mere infant still. But this child has been growing up very, very fast. Few people today would doubt that management is essential. Indeed, even in China, where under Mao management was clearly taboo, there is now a sharp shift. Today, management and managers are the essential key resource for economic and social development (Ngige, 2014).

Management is a factor of production and an economic resource, and the arts and sciences of management appear to provide the best opportunity for increase in productivity. The vast majority of productivity improvements (60%) are within the purview of assertive, innovative, entrepreneurial managers functioning in their role as productivity catalysts Heizer and Render in (Ngige, 2014). However, with this acceptance of management as a key function in society have come ever increasing demands/challenges on the manager. Thus, the global managerial challenges facing organizations today illustrate the rapid change and unpredictability that all managers face today in contemporary times and in the future in managing organizations. Most organizations have survived and thrived because of the remarkable management talent of their managers and management in overcoming global managerial challenges. Hence, managers and management can have the most remarkable effects on organizations if they take into cognizance these issues/challenges facing management today in organizations. Conversely, businesses with untrained and unrepentant staff to cope with these challenges will lose market share and will ultimately be chased out of business by their competitors. Nevertheless, the effect of good management in coping with these challenges on companies is nothing short of remarkable (Ngige, 2014). Organizations need to grapple with a number of revolutionary forces/challenges; boosting the productivity of resources, employing resources where results are, staying ahead and coping with change/accelerating product and technological changes, motivating knowledge workers/disenchanting employees or rather trends towards knowledge workers and the information age, and globalized competition. Challenges like these have changed the playing field on which firms must compete. In particular, they have dramatically increased the need for firms to be responsive, flexible, and capable of competing and reacting rapidly in a global marketplace (Ngige, 2014).

The role of managers in ensuring excellent organizational performance cannot be over emphasized. Adequate motivation, suitable work environment, compensation, efficient communication between managers and subordinates play an important role in promoting this goal. Planning and organization of work is also very crucial in organizational attainment. Some researchers have argued that the most common problems affecting organizational performance in Nigeria business and other institutions are poor attitude to work among workforce, inefficiency as well as ineffectiveness of leaders in most places, though others share a contrary view.. In the wake-

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up call to address this issue, management practitioners in Nigeria have embarked on series of studies in an attempt to establish the relationship between effective leadership and organizational performance. Some found out that effective leadership styles are positively related to organizational performance while others have a different view. Still there is no empirical evidence to show how effective leadership styles impacts on organizational performance (Edoka, 2012). Again, given our cultural background, educational qualifications, environmental factors it is still not too clear how effective a manager can be if he must combine the three types of leadership styles to achieve high performance in Organizations (Usoro, 2008).

Given this scenario, this study will be important in that it tries to fill this gap.

Despite the above, we should note that individuals have their needs to satisfy and that is why they offered their labours to become organizational members and the extent to which they are committed to the organization depends on the degree of their conviction that their membership of the organization will enable them realize their predetermined objectives. In this case, the support an organization gets from the individuals will be based on the realization that by doing that, his personal objectives and goals will be met, otherwise his interest in the organization will wane. Speaking in the same vein Edem (2002), observes that failure or success of an organization, which affect the subordinates, the customers and agencies within and outside the organization. Although there is no standard method through which a manager can be effective in achieving high performance in an organization but that what is required is the modification and the combination of the variables that make a leader effective if the goals and objectives of the organization have to be realized (Edem, 2002). It is against this background that this study was carried out to assess the effect of global managerial challenges on organizational performance of fast-food industry in Abia State.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEMS

In order to secure viability and growth, a crucial goal for any organization is to perform well and achieve good results. There can be many means to achieve this, and one possibility is to overcome the managerial challenges of the organization in such a way that they give rise to increased performance and improved organizational results. But the problem is, to what extent do managers recognize this fact that employees are veritable asset in Organizations and that they should be adequately motivated so that they can give their best to ensure high performance? Again, the manager's behaviour and leadership style in most organizations which believe that workers could be treated anyhow as a result of unemployment situation in the country which makes job switch difficult has resulted in the hardship workers face in their places of work in Nigeria. The autocratic style of leadership has a negative impact and affects the organizational culture which in turn affects organizational performance and commitment. So given this situation, bad leadership and unhealthy relationship among employers and employees bears a far-reaching effect on the organization.

Furthermore, some researchers are of the opinion that the most common global managerial problems affecting organizational performance in Nigeria businesses and other institutions are poor leadership style, recession, dwindling economy, poor attitude to work among the workforce, inefficiency and ineffectiveness of leaders in most places. Others still belief that organizations in Nigeria are managed through leadership styles and behaviours

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that are strange to typical Nigerian culture. But the problem is, to what extent do managers recognize this fact that managerial challenges can occur at any time even when they least expect it? and they should be adequately addressed and handled so that it will not affect the performance of the organization.

Also, some researchers are of the opinion that the most common global challenges affecting organizational performance in Nigeria businesses and other institutions are poor attitude to work among the workforce, inefficiency and ineffectiveness of managers in most places, others still believe that organizations in Nigeria are managed through leadership styles and behaviours that are strange to typical Nigerian culture. Poor working conditions and unskilled managers that are managing most organizations is also a challenge that affects the organizational performance of most organizations.

In view of the above contending issues, it was necessary to look at the effect of global managerial challenges on organizational performance in Nigeria using Fast-foods Abia State as a case study.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this study is to assess the effect of global managerial challenges on organizational performance. The specific objectives were as follows; to:

- i. determine the effect of the leadership behavior/styles on the survival of fast-foods in Abia State.
- ii. examine the extent to which the management structure of fast-foods influences the sustainability of fast-foods in Abia State.
- iii. determine the effect of work conditions on the profitability of fast-foods in Abia State.
- iv. ascertain the effect of managerial competence on the effectiveness of fast-foods in Abia State.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK Leadership Behavior/Styles

Leadership behaviour/style is a global managerial challenge facing most organizations. Some managers of organizations introduce new cultures and leadership styles that the employees are not familiar with which makes most employees weak emotionally. Ability to lead and willingness to follow are based on leadership styles. Leadership behaviour/style is the manner and approach of providing direction, implementing plans, and motivating people. Prasad states that Lewin led a group of researchers to identify different styles of leadership. This study has been very influential and established three major leadership styles. The three major styles of leadership are:

- Authoritarian or autocratic
- Participative or democratic
- Delegative or free reign (Abbas & Yaqoob, 2009)

Authoritarian (Autocratic)

This style is used when leaders tell their employees what they want done and how they want it accomplished, without getting the advice of their followers. Some of the appropriate conditions to use are when you have all the information to solve the problem, you are short of time, and your employees are well motivated. Some people tend to think of this style as vehicle for yelling, using demeaning language, and leading by threats and abusing their power. This is not the authoritarian style, rather it is an abusive unprofessional style called bossing people around. It has no place in a leader's repertoire. The authoritarian style should normally only be used on rare occasions (Prasad, 2004 cited in Edoka, 2012).

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Participative (Democratic):

This style involves the leader including employees in the decision-making process (determining) what to do and how to do it). However, the leader maintains the final decision-making authority. Using this style is not a sign of weakness, rather it is sign of strength that employees will respect which will affect the performance of the organization positively. This is normally used when the leader has part of the information and the employees on the other side have the other parts. A leader is not expected to know everything and this is why organizations leadership and management have to employ knowledgeable and skillful employees. Using this style of mutual benefit, it allows them to become part of the team and allows you to make better decision. Based on the above the Fast-foods in Umuahia should be jointly managed together if the expected results should be realized (Prasad 2004 cited in Edoka, 2012).

Delegative (Free Reign):

In this style, the leader allows the employees to make the decisions. However, the leader is still responsible for the decisions that are made. This is used when employees are able to analyse the situation and determine what needs to be done and how to do it. This is not a style to use so that you can blame others when things go wrong, rather it is a style to be used when one fully trusts and confide in the people below him (Edoka, 2012).

The relationship between Effective Leadership and Organizational Performance. Avery considering the views to several scholars' states that during the past four decades, the impact of leadership styles on organizational performance has been a topic of interest among academics and practitioners working in the area of leadership. This according to him is due largely to the widespread believe that leadership can affect the performance of organizations and that the style of leadership adopted is considered by some researchers to be particularly important in achieving organizational goals, and in working performance among subordinates. Several reasons he adds indicate that there should be a relationship between leadership and performance. The first reason he said relates to practice and that due to today's intensive, dynamic markets feature innovation-based competition, price performance, rivalry, decreasing returns, and the creative destruction of existing competence, scholars and practitioners in his view are of the opinion that effective leadership behaviours can facilitate the improvement of performance when organizations face these new challenges (Avery, 2009).

Understanding the effects of leadership on organizational performance Zhu et al, (2005) in Avery (2009) is also important because leaders in their view is viewed by researchers as one of the key driving forces for improving a firm's performance; effective leadership to them is seen as a potent source of management development and sustained competitive advantage for organizational performance improvement. In view of this relationships Avery (2009) states that transactional leadership helps organizations achieve their current objectives more efficiently by linking job performance to valued rewards and by ensuring that employees have the resources needed to get the job done. Visionary leaders Avery states creates a strategic vision of some factors, communicate that vision through framing and use of metaphor, model the vision by acting consistently, and build commitment towards the vision. (Zhu et al, 2005 in Avery, 2009) suggest that visionary leadership will result in high levels of cohesion, commitment, trust, motivation, and hence performance in the organizational environments. According to Mehra et al 2016 in Avery (2009) when some organizations seek efficient ways to enable them to outperform others not minding the global challenges, a long' standing approach is to focus on the effects of leadership. This

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is because team leaders are believed to play a pivotal role in shaping collective norms, helping teams cope with their environments and coordinating collective action. These leaders centred perspective has provided valuable insights into the relationship between leadership and team performance (Avery, 2009). Leadership is a process by which one person influences the thoughts, attitudes and behaviours of others. Leaders set a direction for the rest of us; they help us see what lies ahead; they help us visualize what we might achieve, they encourage us and inspire us. Without leadership a group of human beings quickly degenerates into argument and conflict, because we see things in different ways and lean toward different solutions. Leadership helps to point us in the same direction and harness our efforts jointly (Quinn, 2005).

Working Condition

Kohun (2012), defines working condition as an entirety which comprises the totality of forces, actions and other influential factors that are currently and, or potentially contending with the employee's activities and performance. Working condition is the sum of the interrelationship that exists within the employees and the organization in which the employees work. Brenner (2004) was of the opinion that "the ability to share knowledge throughout organizations depends on how the work environment is designed to enable organizations to utilize good working condition as if it were an asset. This helps organizations to improve effectiveness and allow employees to benefit from collective knowledge". In addition, he argued that working condition designed to suit employee's satisfaction and free flow of exchange of ideas is a better medium of motivating employees towards higher productivity.

Working condition plays an important role towards the employees' and organizational performance. Working condition is argued to impact immensely on organizational performance either towards negative or the positive outcomes (Chandrasekar, 2011). In the world, there are international organizations who debate the rights of employee. Most people spend fifty percent of their lives within indoor environments, which greatly influence their mental status, actions, abilities and performance (Dorgan, 2014). Better outcomes and increased productivity is assumed to be the result of better working condition.

Managerial Competence

Managerial competencies are the skills, motives and attitudes necessary to a job, and include such characteristics as communication skills, problem solving, customer focus and the ability to work within a team. While businesses have long been capable of analyzing and utilizing financial and other "hard" assets, the human assets involved in managerial competencies are harder to fit into an equation. While skills and knowledge are a part of a manager's competency that can be measured fairly easily, intangible assets like effective communication and teamwork, while essential, are harder to pin down and evaluate (Je' Czaja, 2017).

Managerial competencies play today an important role in different types of organizations. The aim of enterprises is to move the performance of their employees still further and further. Competencies can detect the differences between average and excellent managers. Perhaps the potential power of an organization is to possess excellent or above average employees, through the elimination of average employees with continual education and the development of their personality. Although there are a lot of theoretical knowledge and concepts, the introduction of a competency approach is not quite a simple process. At first it means a change, with the aim of improving

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performance across the organization. And these facts require a change for each employees (Krajcovicova, Caganova & Cambal, 2012).

Orgarnizational Performance

Performance has been defined by Hellriegel et al (1999) as cited in Oluseyi and Ayo (2009) in their European journal of Economics, finance and administrative science (2009) as the level of an individual's work achievement after having exerted effort. They also present the views of Cummings and Schwab on the same issue who believe that performance is ultimately an individual phenomenon with environmental variables influencing performance primarily through their effect on the individual determinants of performance ability and motivation. There is a direct link between the statement of problems and the objectives stated. That is the researcher wants to discover the effect of leadership behaviour/style on the organizational performance. Leadership style/behaviour is a managerial challenge faced by most organizations across the globe and in Nigeria in particular which in turn affects the performance of the organization. This is because the availability of friendly leadership style and proper motivation will equally lead to high organizational performance and the lack of it will have an opposite effect (Oluseyi & Ayo, 2009).

According to Scherbaum et al, (2016) in Avery (2009) how to measure orgarnizational performance has been a persistent source of debate and critique. They said that previous researches have been heavily criticized for the measures of performance used. Such performance measures according to Hoogh et al (2004) in Avery (2009) includes: knowledge of prior performance, self- reports of commitment to orgarnizational goals, satisfaction with the leader and perceived leader effectiveness. Other researchers such as Koene et al, (2002); in (Avery, 2009) are of the opinion that orgarnizational performance can be done through the use of net profit margin, business unit sales and percentage of goals met regarding business unit percentage of goals met regarding business unit performance. In their view, the above performance method can only be applied to organizations that are profit oriented and that nonprofit making organizations can rely on performance measures using such methods as environmental constraints which may reflect forces outside the control of the leader. Avery also is of the view that several scholars have neglected to focus attention on issues such as the correlation between financial performance, customer satisfaction and employee satisfaction when considering organizational performance and that if the net financial and cost controllable are combined with the environmental constraints, employees and customer satisfaction will enhance the validity of the research work. On the other hand, the customers are not too satisfied as a result of time wasted before service or before response which has resulted in several corps members being rejected which cause frustration among the corps members and lack of satisfaction (Avery 2009).

Performance is considered to be a construction (Henri, 2014) and the purpose of defining this concept is to determine its properties and dimensions. The notion of performance has an abstract character and its definition is made by reference to other concepts, on which we believe that performance is built. A concept is itself an abstraction of observable or measurable facts; certain concepts are at a high level of abstraction, and their explanation is achieved through other concepts, so they are called constructions (Quinn and Rohrbaugh, 2013).

How to Measure Orgarnizational Performance

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Organizational Factors that affect Organization Performance

An attractive and supportive working environment provide conditions that enable employees to perform effectively, making best use of their knowledge, skills and competences and the available resources in order to provide high-quality of organization service. Basing on this study the factors are explained below.

Manager's Support

A manager is also known as a person who is an experienced leader, a person who can solve problem and also the role model at the first level of organizational management (Nijman, 2014). Therefore, as an experience leader, the supervisors had always been involved in conducting a training program. The training program that is being conducted are such as establishing the objectives, selecting the trainer, developing a lesson plans, selecting the program method and techniques that is being used, preparing the materials, scheduling the program and also conduct a training needs analysis. Rabey, (2017) stated that, a supervisor could be a trainer to the employees, as the trainer will assist the employees in getting their job done by guiding employees on the operational process especially when it comes to a new operational procedure. A manager support could lead to positive organizational performance but there is a case that the supervisor had failed in supporting their employees. For example, the miscommunication between employees and the manager in term of delivering the information or process on the job to the employees (Harris et. al., 2000).

In order to gain positive organizational performance, both party in between the employees and managers needs to play their part which is to commit with the relationship. If full commitment is given, it will lead to positive result to the performance from the employees (Blau, 2014).

Job Aid

Rossett and Gauier (2011) stated that, the purpose of job aid is to direct and guide as to enlighten the employees' performance. Job aid also helps in order to support the employees' performance. An example of a military performance had been reviewed by (Duncan 1985) regarding the military reliance on job aids between 1958 and 1972 which is significant and positive contribution toward the military performance. He also stated that based on the results of military analysis, job aid saved money without jeopardizing employees work performance. There are three ways to increase performance based on the job aid (Cavanaugh, 2004). The first way is through the external support which means that the employees need to take leave from work and look for the source as for their reference to their job. The second way is through the extrinsic support. An extrinsic support means that the job aid is being given within the system itself. As for the third way, it is called the intrinsic support. An intrinsic support is an insider or software that is being used as for the efficiency of workflow.

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Physical Work Environment

Physical working environment can result a person to fit or misfit to the environment of the workplace. A physical work environment can also be known as an ergonomic workplace. Researches on the workplace environment need to be done in order to get an ergonomic workplace for every each of the employees. By having this ergonomic physical workplace at their workplace, it will help employees from not getting the nerve injury (Cooper & Dewe, 2004).

Furthermore, McCoy and Evans (2005) stated that the elements of working environment need to be proper so that the employees would not be stressed while getting their job done. In their article, they also stated that the physical element plays an important role in developing the network and relationship at workplace. Result of the employees' performance can be increased from five to ten percent depending on the improvement of the physical workplace design at their workplace (Brill, 1992).

Further, Amir (2010) mentions elements that related to the working environment. There are two main elements which are the office layout plan and also the office comfort. Amir (2010) also stated that a physical workplace is an area in an organization that is being arranged so that the goal of the organization could be achieved.

Performance Feedback

Performance feedback is an information exchange and conflict resolution process between the employee and supervisor. This consists of both positive feedback on what the employee is doing right as well as feedback on what requires improvement. Managers and supervisors will need to be comfortable with working with the whole range of workplace factors that influence employee performance. While the supervisor gives his/her feedback and requirements, the employee enables to give his/her feedback regarding his/her requirements. Although this process is formal, it could be managed informally by gaining closer relations for two sides (Chandrasekar, 2011).

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Workplace Incentives

The organization determines what motivates its employees and sets up formal and informal structures for rewarding employees behaving in the way required. Rewards may consist of a mix of internal rewards, such as challenging assignments, and external rewards, such as higher compensation and peer recognition (Chandrasekar, 2011). Performance of professional employees is poor not only due to working environment factors but also due to lack of human resource management aspect such as recognition of employees who performs well, poor working condition, absence of performance appraisal system and poor feedback on performance outcome. Therefore, significant changes in promotions, compensation and benefits helps in keeping employees satisfied and in turn increases production.

Personality features and characteristics of managers in Modern Industries

In Nigeria, and in other countries in transition, like in most other countries at the similar level of development, industrial companies are specific in their organization and business activity. The organization is based on strong subordination between owner and employees. The success or lack of success in the work of managers is transferred to lower levels of management and so on to the lowest operator. This is why the selection of managers can also be a key factor to the success or failure of a company. Unfortunately, today in Nigeria, managers are selected by criteria that are not always the criteria of success. The results are obvious.

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Manager and objectives of the organization

The selection of managers, from the top to the lowest level, must be grounded above all on expertise the main prerequisite being that a manager would have to know the objectives of the organization he manages. This means that he must know well the method of work as well as the program, aims, tasks, difficulties a company encounters, as well as everything else of importance for the realization of the company's objectives. This must not be interpreted as if a manager is the most knowledgeable person in all the jobs within such an organization. It must not be even thought of his being simultaneously the best typist and the best programmer and the best accountant and the best economist, etc. He has to know the technology of work as well as the job of each of his associates but only to the extent enabling him to coordinate his work with the work of others and thus efficiently carry out the set tasks. It is of essential significance for a manager to have insight into general line, i.e. general direction of work and task in its entirety and not to be lost in certain details and to be able to discern essential from nonessential, important from unimportant (Adedayo, 2017).

Manager and managerial skills

The manager of a industrial company must possess pronounced management ability. Based thereon he must know how to correctly and skillfully allocate jobs and tasks to his associates, coordinate their work and bring it into conformance in order for the tasks and objectives of the company to be quickly and efficiently carried out. This, at the same time, also means the ability to select the most capable specialists and the most adequate tools for the realization of a specific task. That is why this feature should not be identified with professional skill as they are two different matters even more so as there are cases where managers who do not have this skill, although professionally qualified, can significantly disturb proper functioning of an organization. Unfortunately, such cases are numerous in practice simply due to the reason that the talent for management is regarded identical to professional qualifications. A manager has to set pace of performance, i.e. provide timely performance of works which are the task or objective of company (Adedayo, 2017).

Manager and sense for politics

It is said for a manager that he has to have a sense for politics. This should not be interpreted as engagement of a manager in politics in the literal sense of the word but as his feature composed of the skill to find resources which best suit a given political situation and ability to foresee all consequences and effects that the use of such resources will have on the human mind. Managerial position of the top managers of a big industrial company, first and foremost because of the strategic significance of the company, is usually also connected with participation in governing political structures, however, realistically, managers of such companies do not have possibility to actively and successfully work in both organizations (Adedayo, 2017).

Manager and his Intelligence

A successful manager should be intelligent. Nevertheless, it should be noted that a manager, although he, as a rule, should be more intelligent than the people he manages, must not stand out too much by his intelligence. Too big a difference in intelligence causes exceptionally intelligent managers to abandon the role of a manager and either become cultural leaders or remain comprehended. It turned out that too intelligent persons do not succeed as political leaders and managers primarily due to the fact that their values, which they accept in such cases, are

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far above the value of masses. Masses prefer to be lead, even if not so successfully, by less intelligent managers or by managers they can understand, i.e. those who are closer to the masses. Although these conclusions need not be accepted, the fact remains that in everyday life intelligent managers are not always successful in their job (Adedayo, 2017).

Manager and his energy

A successful manager should be energetic. Such a manager is persistent in performance and at the same time sufficiently strong in motivating others and he also counteracts negative tendencies which may occur inside an organization. A manager must always take into account the negative tendencies which represent quite natural occurrence in a life of an organization and must be assiduous in their eradication. It is only natural that members of a collective resist to the organization's new methods and ideas due to bureaucratic and other habits primarily because they bring uncertainty. As a rule, each newly proposed idea encounters resistance which is explained by its being unnecessary, uncertain, insufficiently useful and expensive. Such occurrences must be overpowered both materially and intellectually. In the realization of such ideas, it is important that a manager must not be reluctant as that would lead to the destruction of his authority.

Manager and his courage

To be successful, the manager must be brave. This kind of courage is the one which the manager should express when certain critical moments in the operation of an organization occur and when he has to accept responsibility for undertaking certain ultimate, often unpopular actions. Manager must exhibit certain courage in such situations and unless he does so he will unavoidably lose authority in the eyes of the work collective. In this way cohesion and strength of the organization will be shattered, too (Adedayo, 2017).

Manager and his initiative

To be successful, a manager must be able to take initiative. He should avail of creative initiative. This means that a manager should try to discover, adopt and apply new material resources, new work methods, new organizational decisions, etc. Even if the resources are of not great opportunities, manager must not deceive himself by applying old patterns in organization. He must always strive for finding novelties in his environment. The lack of incentive certainly affects the manager's authority. If manager is not sufficiently incentive his authority will be based only on hierarchical evaluations and discipline but not on the assurance in his capabilities that he deserves such an organization. Initiative does not allow routine and is often said to be a form of bravery in work. This is why a manager must take care of this element. He must have a critical position with respect to the work performed to that moment and endeavor its improvement and rationalization, and must also try to make the work easier, more purposeful and of better quality. He would thereby contribute not only to the efficiency of the organization he manages but also strengthen and enhance his authority. It is very important that a manager must never be completely satisfied either with the work of his associates or his own because that always results in self-satisfaction and work demoralization (Adedayo, 2017).

Manager and his objectivity

To be successful, a manager should be objective in relations with his associates, their successes and failures, always interested in objective reasons without any subjectivism. The manager must always have the same attitude towards all of his associates. He must not regard them with "unequal eyes", i.e. be "indulgent" to some while

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biased, strict and incorrect to others. Nevertheless, this does not mean that people who deserve so owing to their success in work should not be singled out. Manager should reward, commend and stand them out in order to make them a model for others. Those people will then be aware that their work has really been followed up and righteously evaluated and respected which is a good stimulus for better achievement and creation of a suitable ambience for other members of the collective to follow the example and contribute to efficient materialization of the organization's goals. The manager's position must be objective. If it is grounded on sympathies and antipathies then it significantly contributes to the diminishing of manager's authority (Adedayo, 2017).

Participative (Democratic)

This style involves the leader including employees in the decision-making process (determining what to do and how to do it). However, the leader maintains the final decision-making authority. Using this style is not a sign of weakness, rather it is sign of strength that employees will respect. This is normally used when the leader has part of the information and the employees on the other side have the other parts. We should note that a leader is not expected to know everything and this is why organizations leadership and management have to employ knowledgeable and skillful employees. Using this style of mutual benefit, it allows them to become part of the team and allows you to make better decision. Based on the above fast-food industries should be jointly planned together if the expected results should be realized (Edoka, 2012).

Delegative (Free Reign):

In this style, the leader allows the employees to make the decisions. However, the leader is still responsible for the decisions that are made. This is used when employees are able to analyse the situation and determine what needs to be done and how to do it. This is not a style to use so that you can blame others when things go wrong, rather it is a style to be used when one fully trusts and confide in the people below him (Prasad 2004).

The effect of leadership styles and organizational performance.

Leadership is a process by which one person influences the thoughts, attitudes and behaviours of others. Leaders set a direction for the rest of us; they help us see what lies ahead; they help us visualize what we might achieve, they encourage us and inspire us. Without leadership a group of human beings quickly degenerates into argument and conflict, because we see things in different ways and lean toward different solutions. Leadership helps to point us in the same direction and harness our efforts jointly.

Mcshane defines effective leadership as the process of influencing people and providing an environment for them to achieve team or organizational objectives. He states further that effective leadership help groups of people define their goals and find ways to achieve them.

In his view they use power and persuasion to ensure that followers have the motivation and role clarity to achieve specified goals. Effective resources and achieve cooperate objectives more easily (Mcshane, 2003). Similarly, Beleina (1986) as cited in Ezeani (2016) sates that effective leadership is the "art of influencing individual or group activities towards achievement of enterprise objectives (Ezeani, 2016). He went further to state that effective

According to (Mehra et al 2016 in Avery 2008) when some organizations seek efficient ways to enable them to outperform others, a long' standing approach is to focus on the effects of leadership. This is because team leaders are believed to play a pivotal role in shaping collective norms, helping teams cope with their environments and

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coordinating collective action. These leaders centred perspective has provided valuable insights into the relationship between leadership and team performance (Avery, 2008).

Managerial Competence and Organizational Performance

According to Oluseyi and Ayo Leadership, or more specifically effective leadership, is every bit as crucial (if not more so) in African organizations as it is throughout the world. It has been argued that effective leadership has a positive influence on the performance of organizations and it is the performance of many individuals that culminates in the performance of the organizations or in the achievement of organizational goals. Effective leadership is instrumental in ensuring organizational performance (Edoka, 2012). As a result, many leadership theories have been proposed in the last fifty years which are claimed to have influenced the overall effectiveness of the organizations where they have been employed. In competitive world business environment, it is vital that organizations employ leadership styles that enable organizations to survive in a dynamic environment.

Performance they said has been defined by Hellriegel et al (1999) as cited in Edoka, (2012) as the level of an individual's work achievement after having exerted effort. Also, Cummings et al (1973) in Oluseyi and Ayo (2009) believed that performance is ultimately an individual phenomenon with environmental variables influencing performance primarily through their effect on the individual determinants of performance ability and motivation. They also quoted. That is why it has been widely accepted that effective organizations require effective leadership, and organizational performance will suffer indirect proportion to the neglect of this (Oluseyi & Ayo 2009).

Management Structure and Organizational Performance

Yamoah (2013) carried out a study on the relationship between compensation for dedication to work and employee productivity of staffs from the banking industry in Ghana. In order to achieve his objective, a case study approach was used; a descriptive survey was then carried out to collect data from employees of Ghana Commercial Bank in the Greater Accra Region of Ghana. Data was analyzed in terms of descriptive statistics. Pearson chi square was used to test the significance of relationship between employee compensation and productivity. The results however indicated a significant relationship between compensation and productivity. As a result of these, the researcher therefore concluded that the human resource functions of many corporate organizations are challenged to develop and implement effective compensation schemes which will lead to the achievement of organizational goals and thereby enhance increase in employee productivity.

Hameed and Amjad (2009) in a survey of 31 bank branches showed that comfortable and ergonomic office design motivates the employees and increased their performance substantially.

Aisha et al. (2013) in their study "Effects of Working Ability, Working Condition, Motivation and Incentive on Employees Multi-Dimensional Performance" found that the variables incentives, motivation and working conditions have a significant effect on employee performance in an Indonesian university. It is evident from these studies that a good workplace environment plays a very vital towards increasing performance of employees in general.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Path-goal Theory (Propounded by Robert House in 1971)

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The path-goal theory is a widely recognized theoretical development from a contingency approach which is derived from the behaviour and the expectancy framework of motivation theory of Victor Vroom. Although George Poulos and his colleague at the University of Michigan for social Research used path-goal concepts and terminology many years ago for analyzing the impact of managerial challenges on performance the modern development is usually attributed to Martin Evans and Robert House, who at about the same time wrote separate papers on the subject. In essence, the path-goal theory attempts to explain the impact that managerial challenges have on associate motivation, satisfaction and organizational performance. The early theoretical work on the path-goal theory proposed that leaders will be effective by making rewards available to subordinates and by making those rewards contingent on the subordinates' accomplishment of specific goals (Luthans, 2008) in Oluseyin and Ayo (2009). The early path-goal work on managerial challenges led to the development of a theory involving four specific styles of leader behaviour (directive, supportive, participative and achievement) and three types of subordinate attitudes (job satisfaction, acceptance of the leader and expectations about effect, performance reward relationships). It is argued by them that an important part of the manager's job is to clarify for subordinates the kind of behaviour most likely to result in goal accomplishment and positive organizational performance not to impose things on his subordinates. This activity according to Ivancerich is referred to as path clarification (Ivancerich, 2008).

This theory attempts to define the relationships between managerial challenges, employee's work activities and the organizational performance. Leader behaviour is acceptable to subordinates to the degree that they see it as a source of satisfaction now or as a step toward future satisfaction. The introduction of foreign culture by the management team in most organizations which believe that workers could be treated anyhow as a result of unemployment situation in the country which makes job switch difficult has resulted in the hardship workers face in their places of work in Nigeria. This behaviour has an impact on performing and creating organizational culture which in turn affects organizational performance.

Affective Events Theory (Howard M. W. and Russell C., 1996)

The theory was propounded by Howard Weiss and Russel Cropanzano in 1996 (Phua, 2012). The Affective Events Theory explains the link between employees' internal influences and their reactions to incidents that occur in their work environment that affect their performance, organizational commitment and job satisfaction. It proposes that positive-inducing as well as negative emotional incidents at work have significant psychological impact on employees' job satisfaction. The impact results into lasting reactions exhibited through job satisfaction, organizational commitment and job performance.

According to Ashton-James and Ashkanasy (2005) research to date has supported the central tenets of AET that workplace events trigger affective responses in employees and that these affective responses influence workplace cognition and behavior. They assert that AET is both empirically and theoretically, restricted to events that are internal to the organization. The theory also considers how specific events at work other than job characteristics lead to specific emotional and behavioral responses (Briner, 2000). He posits that these events or things that actually happen at work affect the well-being of employees thus affecting their performance.

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EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Edoka, (2012) carried out a study on the impact of leadership challenges on organizational performance in Nigeria using National Youth Service Corps Kogi State office. The evaluation was done through the use of questionnaire and structured interview question, tailored towards: determining the impact of effective leadership on the performance of the organization; assessing the effect of the relationship between effective leadership and organizational performance in promoting maximization of the objectives of the organization examining whether three are leadership obstacles that hamper organizational performance in the Kogi State NYSC; finding out if there are possible way of enhancing organizational performance in the Kogi State NYSC. The study employed descriptive survey research design in the work. The questionnaire was structured in five-point scale in line with the objectives set out to be achieved in the study. The instrument was checked for reliability using test-re-test method. A sample size of 82 was selected from a total population of 103 and stratified random sampling was used to select the respondents. The data generated from the field survey were presented and analysed using quantitative method like frequency distribution tables and simple percentage (%). The test of hypothesis was performed using chi-square statistical test. The result arising from the primary data tested at 0.05 co-efficient interval and degree of freedom revealed that there is positive and significant relationship between effective leadership and organizational performance in NYSC Kogi State. The study also revealed that there are no leadership obstacles that hamper organizational performance in the Kogi State NYSC resulting from the structure of the organization management. However, the study revealed that in-spite of the above, there are other factors that affect organizational performance. These factors are lack of good office, equipment's, insufficient funds and poor work environment. Again, the work also revealed that in the Kogi State NYSC there are possible ways of enhancing organizational leadership for effective performance. Above all, the study revealed that there is no empirical evidence to show the relationship between effective leadership and organizational performance.

Adedayo, (2017) carried out a study on Performance management and employee productivity of selected manufacturing companies in Lagos State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population was 6026 comprising of the entire staff of five selected manufacturing companies in Lagos State. Taro Yamane formula was used to derive the sample size of 490. A structured questionnaire was administered resulting in a response rate of 97.5%. The instrument was validated and the Cronbach's Alpha used for the Pre-test Reliability Analysis of the major constructs ranged between 0.778 and 0.879. The data gathered was analyzed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.0 software involving frequency distributions, linear and multiple regressions. Findings showed that indeed the four context of performance management had a significant effect on employee productivity. Detailed simple linear regression analysis showed that performance appraisal ($F = 39.60$, $R \text{ Square} = 0.077$, $P < 0.05$) at 7.7%; performance feedback ($F = 142.726$, $R \text{ Square} = 0.231$, $P < 0.05$) at 23.1%; employee training ($F = 7.803$, $R \text{ Square} = 0.016$, $P < 0.05$) at 1.6% and compensation ($F = 297.643$, $R \text{ Square} = 0.385$, $P < 0.05$) at 38.5% had a significant effect with employee productivity, however, performance feedback and compensation had the strongest relationship on employee productivity; multiple regression analysis also showed performance management ($F = 79.482$, $R \text{ Square} = 0.402$, $P < 0.05$) at 40.2% had significant effect on employee productivity. The study concluded that Performance Management when well implemented improves employee productivity especially when more emphasis is placed

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on positive feedback and compensation which was proven to have a higher influence on productivity of employees. It was recommended, among others, that manufacturing firms should encourage their members of staff by giving them regular positive feedback and compensate them fairly to improve productivity.

METHODOLOGY Research Design

The study adopted survey design. Survey design is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analysing data from a sample of people or items considered to be representation of the entire population. Nworgu (2016) explained that survey involves a systematic and comprehensive collection of information about the opinions, attitude, feelings, beliefs and behaviour of people. This method of research design was used because it helps in eliciting relevant information/opinion regarding the effects of global managerial challenges on organization performance using representative sample from Fast-foods in Umuahia fast-food from which the result was generalized upon the entire population.

SOURCES OF DATA

The data used in this study are mainly from primary and secondary sources. The secondary sources of data collection used are already published articles/journals, unpublished articles, lesson notes etc. while the primary sources were collected with the use of questionnaire from the staff of Hoffers fast-foods, Crunches fast-foods, Kilimanjaro fast-foods, Jovit fast-foods, De-choice fast-foods, Chicken Republic fast-foods and Shoprite fast-foods respectively in Umuahia.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

Okebaram, (2014) defines a population as a large number of people living in a given geographical location. The population of the study is two hundred and twenty-seven (227) comprising the aggregation of all the staff and management of Hoffers fast-foods, Crunches fast-foods, Kilimanjaro fast-foods, Jovit fast-foods, De-choice fast-foods, Chicken Republic fast-foods and Shoprite fast-foods.

Table 3.3.1 The Study Population

S/N	Selected fast-foods in Umuahia Abia state	Number staff
1	Hoffers fast-foods,	22
2	Crunches fast-foods,	20
3	Kilimanjaro fast-foods,	38
4	Jovit fast-foods,	46
5	De-choice fast-foods,	34
6	Chicken Republic fast-foods and	27
7	Shoprite fast-foods	40
	Total	227

Source: Field Survey, 2023

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SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION

For the purpose of this study, the researcher derived the sample size statically by using Taro Yamani (cited in Ali, Nor, Mudaser & Muhammad, 2017) as follow;

Using the formula; $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$ Where;

$n =$ Sample size

$N =$ Population (227) $e =$ Margin of error (0.05) Thus, the sample size is:

$n = \frac{227}{1+227(0.05)^2}$

$$n = \frac{227}{1+227(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{227}{1+227(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{1+0.57}{227}$$

$$n = \frac{1.57}{227} = 144.58 \quad n = 145 \text{ staff}$$

Therefore, the sample size for this study is 145 staff of selected fast-foods in Umuahia Abia State.

3.5 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The study adopted stratified sampling, whereby each stratum was drawn from a representing unit and to make sure all the entire population are duly represented for an optimal outcome. Each fast-food represent the strata of the population, using Bowley’s proportion technique formula the results are shown below:

$$nh = \frac{nNh}{N}$$

N

Where:

nh = The number of unit allocated to each stratum. Nh = The number of staff in each category n = The total sample size

N = The actual or total population.

Proportional Allocation:

1. Hoffers fast-foods

$$nh = \frac{145 \times 22}{227} = \frac{3190}{227} = 14.05$$

2. Crunches fast-foods

$$nh = \frac{145 \times 20}{227} = \frac{2900}{227} = 12.78$$

3. Kilimanjaro fast-foods

$$nh = \frac{145 \times 38}{227} = \frac{5510}{227} = 24.27$$

4. Jovit fast-foods

$$nh = \frac{145 \times 46}{227} = \frac{6670}{227} = 29.38$$

5. De-choice fast-foods

$$nh = \frac{145 \times 34}{227} = \frac{4930}{227}$$

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$$227 = \frac{227}{10.4} = 21.72$$

6. Chicken Republic fast-foods

$$nh = \frac{145 \times 27}{3915}$$

$$227 = \frac{227}{13.2} = 17.25$$

7. Shoprite fast-foods $nh = \frac{145 \times 40}{5800} = \frac{227}{8.8} = 25.55$

Table 3.4.1: Selected fast-foods in Umuahia Abia state and proportion size considered

	Population	Proportion
Hoffers fast-foods,	22	14
Crunches fast-foods,	20	13
Kilimanjaro fast-foods,	38	24
Jovit fast-foods,	46	29
De-choice fast-foods,	34	22
Chicken Republic fast-foods and	27	17
Shoprite fast-foods	40	26
Grand Total	227	145

Source: Researcher’s Survey, 2023

DESCRIPTION OF THE RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The key research instrument for this study was structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was structured using 5 points Likert-scale of (Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree). Also the questionnaire was grouped into two sections, section A and section B containing the respondents profile and questions respectively.

VALIDITY OF THE RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

To certify that the research instruments used in this study are valid, the researcher ensured that the instrument measure the concepts they are supposed to measure. A proper structuring of the questionnaire and conducted a pre-test of every question contained in the questionnaire to ensure that they were valid through the researcher supervisor and other expert validators in the study area.

RELIABILITY OF THE RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The reliability of the instrument was established with a trial test administered to 10 staff of Mr. Biggs in Owerri, Imo State at two consecutive intervals of two weeks. This was so because, these respondents in Owerri, Imo State have similar experience regarding the effect of global managerial challenges on organizational performance and they are not part of the study. The reliability of the instrument was determined by using Cronbach’s Alpha. The co-efficient alpha for the instrument is 0.803 which shows that the instrument is highly reliable. $\alpha = \frac{N \cdot C}{V + (N - 1) \cdot C}$

$$\alpha = \frac{N \cdot C}{V + (N - 1) \cdot C}$$

METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The mean was used to answer research question 1-4 in the likert scale application. The hypotheses were tested using Regression and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 0.05. For answering research questions, 3.00 was used

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as cut off point which was gotten by adding the 4-point rating scale and dividing by 4 ($5+4+3+2+1 = 15/5 = 3.00$). Any item with mean score of 3.00 or above were regarded as agreed while any item with mean score of 2.90 or below were regarded as disagreed. The decision on the responses of the research question two was guided by the real limit numbers which include 1.0 – 1.49 VLE, 1.50 – 2.49 LE, 2.50 – 3.49 HE, 3.50 – 4.0 VHE.

For hypotheses testing, the hypothesis of no significant difference was rejected where the Pvalue was less than the alpha-value of 0.05 but not rejected where P-value is equal to or greater than the alpha-value of 0.05 level of significance.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

QUESTIONNAIRE DISTRIBUTION

Distribution of Questionnaire to Staff of Fast-foods in Umuahia and Response Rate.

Respondents	Distributed questionnaires	% Valid & Returned questionnaires	% Invalid and returned	% Not Returned
Hoffers fast-foods	14 (9.66)	13 (10.00)	1 (14.29)	0 (0.00)
Crunches fast-foods	13 (8.97)	13 (10.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
Kilimanjaro fast-foods	24 (16.55)	21 (16.15)	1 (14.29)	2 (18.18)
Jovit fast-foods	29 (20.0)	25 (19.23)	2 (28.57)	2 (18.18)
De-choice fast-foods	22 (15.17)	20 (15.38)	1 (14.29)	1 (9.09)
Chicken Republic fast-foods	17 (11.72)	16 (12.31)	0 (0.00)	1 (9.09)
Shoprite fast-foods	26 (17.93)	22 (16.92)	1 (14.29)	3 (27.27)
Total	145 (100)	130 (89.66)	6 (4.14)	9 (6.21)

Source: Field survey, 2023

Table 4.1.1 above, shows the distribution of questionnaire to respondents. From the table it can be seen that out of the total 145 questionnaires distributed only 130 were actually completed and returned valid constituting 89.66%, while a total of 6 and 9 were either returned not completed or not returned at all constituting 4.14% and 6.21% respectively. Therefore, this analysis is based on 130 questionnaire correctly filled and returned which formed about 89.66% of respondents who co-operated with the researcher. The high percentage of those who cooperated with the researcher shows that they were familiar with the topic under consideration.

Distribution of respondent by sex

SEX	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Male	43	33.08
Female	87	66.92
Total	130	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

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Table 4.1.2 shows the number of male staffs as 43 which makes up 33.08% of the total number of respondents and 87 females which makes up the remaining 66.92%. This indicates the population is more of female respondent than male.

Distribution of respondent by educational qualification

QUALIFICATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
SSCE, GCE	55	42.31
OND, HND	41	31.58
B.Sc., ACA	16	12.31
M.Sc., MBA	12	9.23
Ph.D.	7	5.38
Total	130	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

Table 4.1.3 reveals the qualification of the respondents. 42.31% has the SSCE and GCE, 31.58% has OND and HND, 12.31% has B.Sc. and ACA, 9.23% has M.Sc. and MBA and while 5.38% has Ph.D. This shows that the respondents have knowledge of the variables used for this study.

Distribution of respondent by marital status

MARITAL STATUS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Married	28	21.54
Single	72	55.38
Widow	14	10.77
Divorced/Separated	16	12.31
Total	130	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

Table 4.1.4 reveals the marital status of the respondents. 21.54% has the Married, 55.38% has Single, 10.77% has Widow, and 12.31% has Divorced/Separated. This shows that the respondents are of different marital levels.

TEST OF HYPOTHESES

Regression results determining the effect of the leadership behaviour/styles on the survival of fast-foods in Abia State.

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound

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1	(Constant)	.498	.132		3.785	.000	.238	.758
	Leadership behaviour/ styles	.890	.030	.936	30.132	.000	.832	.949

R = 0.936
 R-Square = 0.876
 Adjusted R-Square = 0.875
 Std. Error of the Estimate = 0.34559
 Durbin-Watson = 0.353 F-Statistics = 907.919
 T-Statistic (df₁ = 1 & df₂ = 128) = 30.132

a. Dependent Variable: Survival of Fast-foods in Abia State

b. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership behaviour/styles

Source: Researcher’s Estimation 2023 SPSS version 25.0 Significance @ 95 confidence level

(See SPSS Output –Appendix I)

As seen in the tables 4.3.1 the regression results showed that the estimated coefficient of the regression parameters has positive sign and thus conform to our a priori expectation, the R- square value of 0.876 which is the coefficient of determination covers 87.6% of the sample variation in the dependent variable is explained or caused by the explanatory variable while

12.4% is unexplained. This remaining could be caused by other factors or variables not built into the model. The high value of R-square is an indication of a good relationship between the dependent and independent variables, meaning that there is a strong positive correlation between Leadership behaviour/styles and Survival of Fast-foods in Abia State. This means that an increase in the independent variables will bring about credibility in the dependent variable. The regression equation ($Y = 0.498 + 0.890LBS + e$) shows that the survival of Fast-foods in Abia State will always depend on a positive constant factor of 0.498 regardless of the existence of other leadership behaviour/styles determinants. Every unit increase of leadership behaviour/styles will enhance survival of Fast-foods in Abia State by a factor of 0.890. The R² value of 0.875 means that 87.5% of the variations in banks productivity is explained by employees’ reward while the 12.5% is explained by other variables indicating that the model is a good predictor. 0.34559 indicates its Standard Error of the Estimate, while Durbin Watson Statistic of 0.353 show the degree of no autocorrelation of variables in the region or partition curve. The F-Statistics of 907.919 measures the goodness of fit of the model which is greater than 2.5 rule of thumbs. The calculated t-Statistic remains 30.132 at (df₁ = 1 & df₂ = 128).

Hypothesis one

H0₁: Leadership behaviour/styles does not have any significant effect on the survival of Fast-foods in Abia State.

H₀ = B₁ = 0. Test the hypothesis that all slope coefficients are equal to zero. H₁ ≠ B₁ ≠ 0. Test the hypothesis that not all slope coefficients are equal to zero.

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With reference to table above, the calculated t-statistics of 30.132 is greater than the critical value (i.e. 1.984), the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative accepted. This means that, leadership behaviour/styles has significant effect on the survival of Fast-foods in Abia state.

DISCUSSIONS OF RESULTS

Going by the statistical findings, it was observed in the first hypothesis that leadership behaviour/styles has significant effect on the survival of Fast-foods in Abia State. This is in consonance with the investigations of Edoaka, (2012) who carried out a study on the impact of leadership challenges on organizational performance in Nigeria using National Youth Service Corps Kogi State office. The study employed descriptive survey research design in the work. The questionnaire was structured in five-point scale in line with the objectives set out to be achieved in the study. The instrument was checked for reliability using test-re-test method. A sample size of 82 was selected from a total population of 103 and stratified random sampling was used to select the respondents. The data generated from the field survey were presented and analysed using quantitative method like frequency distribution tables and simple percentage (%). The test of hypothesis was performed using chi-square statistical test. The result arising from the primary data tested at 0.05 co-efficient interval and degree of freedom revealed that there is positive and significant relationship between effective leadership and organizational performance in NYSC Kogi State. However, the work also revealed that in the Kogi State NYSC there are possible ways of enhancing organizational leadership for effective performance.

In the second hypothesis, managerial structure has significant influence on the sustainability of Fast-foods in Abia State. This also conformed to the work of Adedayo, (2017) who carried out a study on Performance management and employee productivity of selected manufacturing companies in Lagos State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population was 6026 comprising of the entire staff of five selected manufacturing companies in Lagos State. Taro Yamane formula was used to derive the sample size of 490. A structured questionnaire was administered resulting in a response rate of 97.5%. The instrument was validated and the Cronbach's Alpha used for the Pre-test Reliability Analysis of the major constructs ranged between 0.778 and 0.879. The data gathered was analyzed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.0 software involving frequency distributions, linear and multiple regressions. Findings showed that indeed the four context of performance management had a significant effect on employee productivity. Detailed simple linear regression analysis showed that performance appraisal ($F = 39.60$, $R \text{ Square} = 0.077$, $P < 0.05$) at 7.7%; performance feedback ($F = 142.726$, $R \text{ Square} = 0.231$, $P < 0.05$) at 23.1%; employee training ($F = 7.803$, $R \text{ Square} = 0.016$, $P < 0.05$) at 1.6% and compensation ($F = 297.643$, $R \text{ Square} = 0.385$, $P < 0.05$) at 38.5% had a significant effect with employee productivity, however, performance feedback and compensation had the strongest relationship on employee productivity; multiple regression analysis also showed performance management ($F = 79.482$, $R \text{ Square} = 0.402$, $P < 0.05$) at 40.2% had significant effect on employee productivity. In the third hypothesis, work conditions has significant effect on the profitability of Fast-foods in Abia state. This equally supports the study of Nwonu, (2014) who carried out a study on the effect of working conditions on employee performance using descriptive survey design. This is Descriptive research where data are usually collected, organized and analyzed and then described as they exist without interfering with them. It also adopted a Descripto-Explanatory research design; a combination of both descriptive and explanatory research designs. A

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review of past studies shows that improved working conditions impacts positively on employees' performance. Similarly, occupational safety and healthy environment also contributes to the attainment of organizational goals. It was also found that health risk reduced, cost related to absenteeism and sick days was brought to the barest minimum. Also, there is a positive correlation between working condition and improved performance as well as competitive edge. Consequently, the study also discovered from the review that provision and maintenance of facilities reduced staff turnover, fewer occupational injuries, improved service levels, job satisfaction among employees as well as improved relationship between employees and their employers.

Lastly, in the fourth hypothesis, managerial competence has significant effect on the effectiveness of fast-foods in Abia State. This is in relation with the research study of Ncube, (2019), who in a study investigated the effects of managerial competencies on the performance of SMMEs in Makana Municipality, in the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa. The study followed a quantitative research approach. Data was collected using the survey method by way of a self-administered questionnaire, which was distributed to a sample of 96 SMME owners and managers in Makana Municipality. It was found that communication competencies, planning competencies, self-management competencies, and global awareness competencies have an effect on the performance of the SMMEs.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This study analysed the effect of global managerial challenges on organizational performance (a study of selected fast-food industry in Umuahia Abia state). Descriptive research design was adopted. A total of 145 questionnaires was administered to the staff of selected fast-food industry in Umuahia Abia state. Frequency distribution and percentages was determined, the hypotheses were tested using regression analysis and Spearman correlation coefficients with the help of SPSS version 25.0. The findings indicates that;

- i) Leadership behaviour/styles have significant effect on the survival of Fast-foods in Abia State.
- ii) Managerial structure has significant influence on the sustainability of Fast-foods in Abia State.
- iii) Work conditions have significant effect on the profitability of Fast-foods in Abia state.
- iv) Managerial competence has significant effect on the effectiveness of fast-foods in Abia State.

CONCLUSION

Managerial challenges in an organization represents a significant responsibility. All interested parties will depend on the management decisions. In seeking a return, employees' satisfaction at work and career development opportunities, and to feel proud and confident in the workplace; customers and partners are seeking services and solutions which meet their requirements and deliver real value. This study focused on the different dimensions of global managerial challenges on performance of organizations, namely, leadership behaviour/styles, managerial structure, work conditions and managerial competence. Based on the hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance using ANOVA, it can be concluded that leadership behaviour/styles have effect on the performance of Fast-foods in Abia State, managerial structure has influence on the performance of Fast-foods in Abia State, work conditions have effect on the performance of Fast-foods in Abia State and managerial competence have effect on the performance of fast-foods in Abia State.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

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- 1) CEO/Manager of fast-food should possess good leadership behaviour/styles in order to improve on the survival of Fast-foods in Umuahia as initiating structure and consideration, motivation and vision, employee-oriented and production-oriented, coercion and motivation are variable tools for organizational survival.
- 2) There is need to improve and continuously adjust to good and effective managerial structure to help carry out works and other responsibilities effectively and efficiently by employees of Fast-foods in Umuahia Abia state in other to foster maintain their sustainability.
- 3) Fast-foods in Abia state should regularly review and set in motion good working conditions such as; work place structure, physical environment, working time issues, job content, social environment and psychosocial risk and work-related outcomes such as job satisfaction which motivate an employee and in turn push them for bigger achievement and enhance profitability of Fast-foods in Abia state.
- 4) Lastly fast-foods in Abia State should continuously train and retrain their staff and adapt all factors/dimensions of managerial competence such as; external/strategic, interpersonal, personal, contextual adaptability, developmental approach and effective communication in running their business impact on their effectiveness.

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